

PET Demonstrator for a Human Brain Scanner Based on Monolithic Detector Blocks

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Abstract – We have implemented and evaluated a positron emission tomography (PET) demonstrator using two monolithic detector blocks operating in coincidence with dedicated application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) readout. Each detector is composed of a monolithic lutetium yttrium orthosilicate (LYSO) scintillator coupled to a pair of Hamamatsu S8550-02 APD arrays. The front-end electronics of this demonstrator is based on the VATA240 ASIC readout, which sums the charge provided by each row and column of the APD array. The ASIC has been characterized obtaining a noise per row or column less than 2000 electrons rms with the APD at its inputs and a good linear response in the range from 5 fC to 30 fC. We have acquired energy spectra of ^{22}Na and ^{137}Cs radioactive sources, achieving energy resolutions between 13.2% and 14.1% full width at half maximum (FWHM) at 511 keV. We have estimated the interaction position over the surface of the monolithic blocks using Neural Networks (NN) position determining algorithms, obtaining spatial resolutions at the detector level down to 2.1 mm FWHM. By using this detector technology and electronics we have achieved images of point sources with spatial resolutions as good as 2.1 mm FWHM for filtered back projection (FBP) reconstructions methods with single slice rebinning (SSRB). Based on the results obtained with this demonstrator, we are developing a PET insert for existing magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) equipment, to be installed in a collaborating hospital and used for clinical PET-MRI of the human brain.

I. INTRODUCTION

WE are developing a novel positron emission tomography (PET) scanner dedicated to the study of the human brain, to be used in a clinical environment. The proposed scanner will have the shape of a cylindrical insert to be installed inside the bore of existing magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scanners, thus profiting from the patient management system of the latter and allowing the acquisition of both functional and anatomical images, furthermore eliminating the problems related to coregistration issues [1]. The blending of PET and MRI images [2] opens new perspectives in imaging diagnosis since both images present complementary features. While

PET provides functional information with high sensitivity in metabolic processes and neuroreceptor activity, MRI has different methods for imaging anatomical details and also the ability to show additional information such as cerebral blood flow measurements, the structure of nerve fibers *in vivo*, or the measurement of specific biochemical compounds *in vivo*; provided by functional MRI (fMRI) [3], diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) [4] or magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) [5], respectively. The coupling of PET and MRI features several advantages with respect to the present state-of-the-art multimodality technique for simultaneous functional and anatomical imaging of the human brain, PET merged with computed tomography (CT). In particular, it provides better soft tissue contrast and differentiation of grey and white matter, together with the elimination of the risk associated to the ionizing radiation delivered to the patient derived from a brain CT scan [6]. In addition, MRI images can also be used for attenuation and scatter corrections of PET images, which demonstrate the feasibility of MRI-based equipments as a real alternative to CT [7]. For this purpose, we are designing our scanner with magnetically-compatible APDs and a selection of electronic components which allow operation within the MRI. Our detector design is based on monolithic scintillator blocks coupled to APD matrices, which present high active volumes, reduce the detector costs and deliver good spatial resolutions [8],[9]. In these detectors we determine the entry point of the gamma ray over the detector surface from the measured light distribution, using neural network (NN) algorithms [8]. The different patterns of light are read out by a custom application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) which delivers an amplitude proportional to the charge generated by the APDs and is also capable of withstanding strong magnetic fields. The expected operation of the complete scanner has been studied through Monte Carlo simulations, showing that our detector design is capable of dealing with the single and coincidence event rates expected during clinical PET examinations of the human brain [10]. In this work we describe the laboratory demonstrator used to validate the detector block concept and present the images obtained using analytic reconstruction techniques.

II. THE HUMAN BRAIN PET SCANNER

A. Overall description

The proposed BrainPET scanner will consist of 4 rings with 52 detector blocks, each one composed of two independent radiation sensors stacked along the radial direction (Fig. 1), comprising two layers of detecting material in order to

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enhance the overall scanner efficiency [9],[10]. The dimensions of the scanner are determined by considering a 40 cm inner diameter for the PET detectors and an outer diameter of 60 cm to allow its use as an insert for an existing MRI system.

B. Mechanical design

The mechanical design of the scanner is modular, with 52 identical azimuthal modules each containing 4 double-layer detector blocks (detailed below) stacked along the axial axis, together with its front-end readout and data acquisition processor modules. In order to improve the uniformity of the sensitivity along the axial direction, and to reduce the effect of the gaps between adjacent detector blocks (4 mm), every second module is displaced 5 mm axially with respect to the other (e.g. as in the Raytest ClearPET scanner [11]). With this detector arrangement the axial field of view (FoV) of the scanner is 91 mm, sufficient for single-bed acquisition of individual brain structures such as the hippocampus in the diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease or the striatum in Parkinson's disease [12]. The reduced axial FoV is primarily due to budget limitations; however the modular design of the scanner allows to increase it by adding extra detector rings in the future.

Fig. 1. 3D renderings of a double-layer detector block (left) and the complete BrainPET scanner with 208 identical blocks (right).

C. Detector block design

The general geometry of a detector block is shown on the left of Fig. 2. There are two layers of LYSO:Ce scintillators, where each crystal in the detector block has a trapezoidal shape and is independently coated with a diffuse white reflector and coupled to a pair of magnetically-compatible Hamamatsu S8550-02 APD arrays, each comprising 32 pixels with an active area of $1.6 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^2$ at a pitch of 2.3 mm. The 8×8 matrix of pixels from both APD arrays is read out by a single custom ASIC, described in more detail below.

In a previous work [10] we have carried out detailed Monte Carlo simulations for the double layer full-ring design, where we reported the expected differences in detector performance between the inner and the outer layer, concluding that gamma ray interactions are most likely to occur in only one layer of the detector block, depositing its full energy either on the front

or on the back layer. Therefore interactions on the front layer only reduce the outer layer counting rate with no significant effects on degradation of image quality. Moreover, the studies of the influence of different instrumentation parameters [13] as well as the robustness of the detector blocks against temperature fluctuations have also been performed both by Monte Carlo simulations and laboratory measurements [14].

In our laboratory demonstrator we have considered detector blocks with only a single detector layer, so that the individual characterization of the front and the back layer detector geometries could be made easily (see photograph and caption of Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Engineering drawing of the double layer trapezoidal detector block design showing the dimensions in mm of the transverse and radial directions in the human Brain PET scanner (left); photograph of the trapezoidal detector block implemented in the laboratory demonstrator, corresponding to the inner layer (right).

D. Front-end electronics

The front-end electronics of the BrainPET scanner will be based on the VATA241 ASIC, which has been characterized in [15] and is the updated version of the VATA240 ASIC used in the demonstrator presented in this work. Both ASICs have been designed and manufactured by the company Gamma Medica-Ideas Norway (GM-I) in Oslo, which has also developed other ASICs for combining nuclear medicine with MRI systems [16].

The front-end electronics of the demonstrator is based on the VATA240 ASIC, which has 64 low noise charge sensitive preamplifiers, 16 slow shapers and a fast shaper, and is controlled with low-voltage differential signaling (LVDS) via a peripheral component interconnect (PCI) bus by setting 191 bits in a configuration mask register. The 64 pixels of the APD matrices were dc-connected to the ASIC preamplifiers, and after 16 parallel summing stages, 16 slow shapers are ac-coupled to provide energy information through semi-gaussian waveforms with a peaking time of 190 ns and shaping times on the order of $1 \mu\text{s}$. All of the 16 slow shapers have an internal simultaneous sample and hold. The fast shaper fires a common trigger with a leading edge discriminator. This ASIC provides an amplification of $20 \mu\text{A}/\text{fC}$ for a dynamic range of 30 fC per each row or column and generates differential analog output currents and a trigger signal whenever the total charge is above a user defined threshold, typically chosen to correspond to 350 keV energy deposition on the scintillators. Whenever a trigger signal is generated, the ASIC samples the values corresponding to the analog sums of the 8 rows and 8 columns of its 64 input matrix, together with the total analog sum, and holds these values at its outputs for a time of the order of 300 ns. A more detailed description of the front-end

electronics used for each PET detector block can be found in [17]. Moreover, in order to improve the timing resolution of the VATA240 whereas preserving the basic architecture design from the described ASIC, the new VATA241 ASIC has been designed featuring a constant fraction discriminator (CFD).

Fig. 3 – Photograph of the ASIC used for the readout of the laboratory demonstrator. The ASIC dimensions are 8.0 mm by 6.5 mm.

E. Principle of operation of a monolithic detector block

Each scintillator crystal of a double-layer detector block operates as an independent detector, so that when a single incident 511 keV gamma impinges on the block only one of the crystals may generate a trigger, never both of them at the same time. Under PET data taking, whenever a positron annihilation occurs, two 511 keV photons are emitted in opposite directions. If they interact with a detector block, the signals from the 64 APD pixels forming an 8×8 matrix collecting the light from the corresponding scintillator are read out by the custom ASIC which sums the values at its inputs along 8 rows and 8 columns. The information corresponding to each of these events acquired with a single trigger can be interpreted as a pair of two-dimensional profiles of the light detected by the APD matrices along two perpendicular axis (8 rows + 8 columns), together with the total charge collected, proportional to the energy deposited in the crystal. Each profile is fed to a neural network (NN) algorithm, which is capable of providing the point of entrance over the surface of the crystal with 2 mm full width at half maximum (FWHM) spatial resolution [8],[9],[17]. In this work we used a two-step algorithm with a global neural network (NN) of two hidden layers with four neurons each, followed by a local NN of the same structure, wherein the latter is trained with the points located in a 5 mm interval around the estimated position provided by the global NN. The result of this processing defines the point of entrance (PoE) of the incident gamma at the surface of a detector block, a point uniquely determined in 3D space (two orthogonal coordinates given by the NN

algorithms and the third one fixed by the position of the surface of the crystal). In case a coincidence occurs between two detector blocks, a line of response (LoR) is defined by joining the two points of entrance on the surface of both blocks and stored for image reconstruction. The referencing of the points of entrance at the surface of each crystal given by the NN algorithms avoids the need for depth of interaction (DOI) information and thus simplifies the overall performance of the scanner and improves the spatial resolution degradation due to parallax errors at the edges of the field of view [18].

F. Coincidence processing and data acquisition

The coincidence architecture of our PET scanner is based on 52 independent event processor modules which comprise 4 double-layer detector blocks located along the axial direction, a front-end readout composed of 8 ASICs (one for each scintillator crystal) and a Virtex5 field programmable gate array (FPGA). Each event processor module implements a part of a distributed processor, determining when one of the 4 detector blocks of the module is in coincidence with one detector block of a given sector consisting of the 17 detector modules facing the module, namely the one opposite and its 8 neighbors on both sides. This coincidence architecture defines a transversal field of view (FoV) of 185 mm, sufficient for image acquisition of an adult's brain properly positioned on the scanner. Whenever a trigger is generated by one module, the FPGA distributes a global trigger to its corresponding coincidence sector of the ring and processes it with one of the other 17 global triggers which comes from one of its 68 detector blocks. If a coincidence occurs, the FPGA sends a package to an optical Ethernet link in order to store this information in a single PC. The digitized data consists of a time stamp, a detector block identifier and the output signals generated by the custom ASIC digitized by 12-bit analog-to-digital converters (ADC) running at 3 MS/s.

G. Magnetic compatibility issues

Special care has been taken in the electronics design and the election of the components which will be located inside the MRI system, in order to avoid the induction of eddy currents in the electronics or the distortion of the static magnetic field of the imager. We have selected non-magnetic Hamamatsu S8550-02 APD matrices with copper pins, brass APD sockets, and we are assessing the necessity of using capacitors and resistors with Platinum-based terminations (PtAg), since our preliminary measurements with standard terminations have shown a slight distortion of the static field when the front-end board was located outside the radiofrequency (RF) coil, as it occurs in the BrainPET scanner. Previous work of other groups has validated the use of the same APD matrices and scintillators, successfully demonstrating its operation inside a 4 T small animal imager [19]. Moreover, the ASIC technology of our front-end readout has also been tested under high magnetic fields [16]. In the future we will evaluate and fine tune the operation of the detectors under high magnetic fields

in parallel with the phased assembly of our human brain PET scanner.

III. THE LABORATORY DEMONSTRATOR

The performance of double-layer detectors has been studied by detailed Monte-Carlo simulations, with results showing their suitability for the project [10]. In this work we have used trapezoidal LYSO:Ce crystals corresponding to the inner layer of the brain PET scanner, with 10 mm height and 18.5 mm by 21.4 mm in the bottom side, while the top side is 22.4 mm (Fig. 2, right). We wrapped the blocks with a diffuse optical reflector on all sides except one, glued to the APDs with Saint-Gobain BC-600 optical cement [20]. We have evaluated both BC-620 white paint from Saint-Gobain [20] and several layers of Teflon tape as diffuse reflectors for our application.

A. Training setup

Before acquiring the coincidence imaging events, the NN algorithms need to be trained in order to be able to process the light-distribution profiles generated by gamma photons impinging over the crystal at different positions and thus provide points of entrance. A dedicated setup (Fig. 4) was built to carry out the NN training of each radiation sensor, which will later provide imaging results under the same operational conditions.

Fig. 4. Photograph (top) and schematic (bottom) of the laboratory setup used for training the NN algorithms. Each detector is scanned at known incidence positions before PET coincidence data acquisition.

We have used a 0.25 mm diameter ^{22}Na source to define a collimated beam of ~ 1 mm width (according to [13]) with a photomultiplier tube (PMT) aligned with each monolithic block. The beam was scanned at 1 mm steps over each crystal surface by displacing horizontally and vertically the monolithic block placed inside a motorized detector box. We

have determined the center position of each detector by measuring the PMT-detector count rate over the edges of each block. We identified which region of the crystal was being irradiated and we measured a beam width of 1.04 mm FWHM by fitting the coincidence count rate profiles with a sigmoid function at the rectangular edges.

B. Laboratory demonstrator setup

After individually training each detector block, we acquired tomographic imaging data using the prototype shown in Fig. 5, consisting of a simple PET demonstrator based on a pair of monolithic position-sensitive detector blocks located inside water-cooled detector boxes (set at 20°C) and placed face-to-face at the BrainPET nominal distance (40 cm). Each box contains a front-end board with a monolithic block coupled to a pair of APD arrays and a VATA240 ASIC which reads out the charge generated by the APDs, as well as a board which converts the 16 differential analog current signals to voltage single-ended signals and the differential current trigger signal to a transistor-transistor logic (TTL) signal. The coincidence trigger is performed from the triggers of both ASICs converted into nuclear instrumentation module (NIM) signals and sent to a LeCroy 465 coincidence module. When this module fires, a CAEN V2718 module generates a gate signal with a width of 500 ns. This signal is sent to a pair of CAEN V785 ADCs to digitize the data from each row and column of both detector blocks.

Fig. 5. Photograph (top) and schematic (bottom) of the laboratory demonstrator setup showing two detector boxes with aligned monolithic detectors and a rotating source holder at the center. For thermal and electrical stability, and in order to avoid ambient light reaching the scintillators, both detector boxes are closed during operation.

In order to allow the acquisition of coincidence data at different projection angles, a rotating precision stage was placed between the detectors and at 20 cm distance of both. A total of 120 projections at 3° steps were considered for each image. Moreover, a manual micrometer allowed to move the source radially along different positions close to the center of the field of view (FoV). We also motorized the detector boxes in order to obtain a precise alignment of both detector blocks, and to increase the FoV of the system by acquiring data with displaced detectors. We have considered for each detector box its centered position and those of its neighbors at each side, and acquired projection data for all the 9 possible combinations of the 3 positions of each box (center, left neighbor, right neighbor). For each set of images (obtained with the detectors either “centered” or “displaced”) we evaluated the image distortions due to the non-linearity of the NN algorithms close to the edges of the scintillators, and studied the importance of such effects on a complete ring of detectors, where each block always has neighbor blocks at both its sides. Whenever there was a coincidence between the two detectors, the point of entrance of each of the two 511 keV gammas into the detectors was estimated by NN algorithms, and a line-of-response (LoR) was acquired, taking into account the projection angle defined by the rotating source holder and both points of entrance.

C. Imaging tests

The aim of the described prototype was to validate the concept of operation of our BrainPET scanner by imaging different test objects based on the data provided by our integrated front-end electronics. The first imaging tests consisted of measuring the spatial resolution of a single 0.25 mm diameter 1.0 MBq ^{22}Na source placed at different positions. The scans were performed at 2 mm steps, acquiring at least a minimum of 200 000 coincidence events per image. For the second set of measurements, we acquired two simultaneous ^{22}Na point sources of 1.0 mm diameter each, with 370 kBq nominal activity. The sources were placed close to the center of the FoV at different separations (2 mm, 3 mm, 4 mm and 5 mm) and a minimum of 400 000 events per image were acquired. The source which was closer to the center of the FoV remained fixed, whereas the second source was moved to achieve the different separations between both sources.

The spatial resolution values characterize the width of the reconstructed image point spread functions (PSF), by defining the width as its FWHM and the full width at tenth-maximum amplitude (FWTM), based on NEMA standards [21]. At every position of the point source, spatial resolution values are presented for radial and tangential directions. The radial direction is defined along a line that connects the center of the image to the location of the point, and the tangential direction is defined perpendicular with respect to the latter. The response function was formed by summing all one-dimensional profiles that are parallel to the direction of measurement (radial or tangential), within two times the FWHM of the orthogonal directions, through the peak of the

distribution. Each FWHM (resp. FWTM) was determined by linear interpolation between adjacent pixels at half (resp. one tenth) the maximum value of the response function. The maximum value was computed by a parabolic fit using the peak and its two neighbouring points [21].

D. Image reconstruction

After all the projections have been acquired, images were reconstructed using the single slice rebinning (SSRB) [22] method with a slice thickness of 0.5 mm and filtered back projection (FBP) [23] on each plane applying a ramp filter with a cutoff at half the Nyquist frequency. An image matrix of 64×64 pixels, which corresponds to $32 \text{ mm} \times 32 \text{ mm}$, was selected and Amide viewer [24] was used for visualization and renderings of the transverse projections. No extra corrections or filtering techniques were applied.

IV. RESULTS

A. Front-end electronics performance

The measurements were performed by charge injection using a voltage calibration input which can be connected to any channel input. Results show that the linearity of the ASIC in its dynamic range from 5 fC to 30 fC is better than 98%. The non-uniformities in gain between rows or columns are smaller than 5%, not affecting the behavior of our detector blocks since these effects are accounted for by the NN training process. The correlation between the data obtained in rows and columns of the ASIC shows also a good agreement. The row and column noise was measured with and without APD arrays on, obtaining ~ 2000 electrons rms and ~ 1000 electrons rms, respectively. The total power consumption of the ASIC is 450 mW. With regard to timing, we measured ~ 40 ns of time-walk due to the leading edge comparator implemented inside this chip. An update of this ASIC, called VATA241, has been manufactured featuring a CFD for reducing the time-walk of the ASIC used in this prototype demonstrator down to 0.5 ns. The performance of this new ASIC has been characterized in [15], where we have obtained an intrinsic timing resolution in the order of 2 ns.

B. Detector block performance

We have evaluated the detector block performance in terms of its energy, spatial and timing resolution. The energy resolution at the 511 keV peak was measured at different APD reverse bias voltages, achieving the best results for APD gains on the order of 100. Different reflectors have been tested under the same APD bias, showing slightly better results for Teflon wrapped blocks (13.2% FWHM) than for those that were painted white (14.1% FWHM).

With regard to spatial resolution, on Fig. 6 we show the local spatial resolutions and the residual errors (differences between the estimated and real positions) along the longer side of the white painted (Fig. 6, top) or Teflon wrapped (Fig. 6, bottom) detectors. We have averaged the results obtained with 3 different sets of training data for a better appreciation of the trend of the FWHM spatial resolutions and the overall

performance of these monolithic blocks. Both reflectors have similar behavior; local resolution losses occur when the incident photon enters close to the edges of the detector block. The apparent improvement close to the edges is due to the truncation of the local PSFs, which do not present a gaussian profile. Therefore, in border regions the calculated FWHM values do not represent the actual spatial resolution. Moreover, on the last 2 mm from the edges, both detector blocks suffer non-linear effects. The global spatial resolution provided by the NN algorithms was 2.08 mm FWHM for the white painted detector and 2.06 mm FWHM for the Teflon wrapped detector, when considering all the central events located 2 mm or more away from the borders. These values degrade to 2.23 mm FWHM for the white painted block and 2.28 mm FWHM for the Teflon detector when taking into account all the events impinging on the detector due to non-linear effects at the detector borders (Fig. 6). In this case, after correction for the 1.04 mm FWHM test beam width, the global spatial resolution is 1.97 mm FWHM and 2.02 mm FWHM for white painted and Teflon wrapped detector blocks, respectively.

Fig 6. Measured local FWHM resolution before test beam correction and residual errors for different detector blocks, white painted (top) and wrapped with Teflon (bottom).

C. Coincidence operation

We have studied the quality of the data acquired using the coincidence trigger from two detectors. Fig. 7 shows the correlation between the energies deposited in each of the two scintillators with an encapsulated ^{22}Na source placed between the detector boxes (setup in Fig. 5). Results demonstrate a strong correlation, with an intense peak corresponding to most coincidence events having 511 keV deposited in both detectors, as expected (Fig. 7). Outside this peak there are very few events in which one of the two detector collects less (or more) than 511 keV, which can be explained by Compton scattering for 511 keV (or 1274 keV) incident gammas (Fig.8). These results allowed us to conclude that the internal trigger of the ASIC is suitable for PET data taking, according to project specifications.

Fig. 7. Correlation between the energies deposited on each of the two detector blocks operating with a PET coincidence trigger. The intense peak corresponds to events with 511 keV energy deposition in both detectors simultaneously.

Fig. 8. Energy spectra obtained with a ^{22}Na source operating with single and PET coincidence triggers. The measured energy resolution at 511 keV is 13.2% FWHM.

We have measured a timing resolution of 27 ns FWHM under PET coincidence operation using the current front-end

electronics which is based on the ASIC VATA240. We expect to significantly improve the timing resolution of our coincidence setup to a few nanoseconds using the updated ASIC VATA241 [15], which will be included in the front-end electronics for the final BrainPET scanner.

D. Imaging tests with a single ^{22}Na point source

For the imaging reconstruction we took into account all the photons impinging over the entire surface of our monolithic blocks. Due to the reduced active surface of the detectors used on the demonstrator, we acquired the imaging data with the detectors both centered (Fig. 9) and displaced (Fig. 10). Doing so, we not only have increased the transversal FoV of the demonstrator but, and more importantly, have evaluated the effects of the non-linear behavior of the NN positioning algorithms close to the edges of the detector blocks on a complete ring geometry, where each detector will always have neighbor detectors on both sides. We present an example of the superposed results for individual acquisitions of a 0.25 mm diameter ^{22}Na source at different radial positions, both for the projection data from only the two detector boxes centered (Fig. 9, left) and the projection data that include the different combinations obtained with the detectors displaced to the right and left neighbor detector positions (Fig. 10, left), emulating 6 detectors in total. The radial intensity profile of the single point source displaced at different positions at 4 mm steps is also shown for both cases. We measured a distance of 10.43 mm and 11.63 mm with the detectors centered (Fig. 9) and displaced (Fig. 10) resp. for point sources which were separated 12 mm.

Fig. 9. Imaging results at 4 mm steps from a 0.25 mm diameter ^{22}Na point source (left) acquired without displacement of the detectors and its radial profile along the central line (right). It can be shown a distortion in the image and a compression factor of 0.89 due to the non-linearities at the edge of the detector block.

Fig. 10. Imaging results at 4 mm steps from a 0.25 mm diameter ^{22}Na point source at four different positions across the field of view considering also the

projection data obtained with the detectors displaced to the right and left neighbor detector positions: transverse image (left) and radial profile along the center line (right). By increasing the FoV of our demonstrator we avoid both distortion and imaging compression effects.

Therefore, it can be seen that an extended FoV and the present of neighbor detectors at the sides of a single block is sufficient to correct the image compression effects due to non-linearities close to the edges of the detectors which is observed for centered detectors. From these results we can infer that the complete ring geometry will not suffer from compression effects and that the reconstructed images will be free from distortions.

Fig. 11 shows the radial and tangential spatial resolutions profiles at 8 different distances from the center of the FoV, along positive and negative radial axis, with displaced detectors. We achieved spatial resolutions from 2.29 mm to 2.64 mm FWHM for the radial direction and from 2.12 mm to 2.24 mm FWHM along the tangential direction. The detectors were not displaced in the axial axis due to mechanical limitations of our setup. The measured FWTM was as good as 3.9 mm and 4.7 mm FWTM for tangential and radial directions, respectively.

Fig. 11. Spatial resolution (FWHM and FWTM) obtained with displaced detectors and measured at different positions along the radial direction of our PET demonstrator.

E. Resolving power of the demonstrator

We have also analyzed the imaging capabilities of our demonstrator with extended sources, considering the acquisition of two simultaneous ^{22}Na sources of 1 mm diameter. One source was fixed while the other was moved away from the center of the FoV, resulting in 2 mm, 3 mm, 4 mm and 5 mm separations between sources. We can appreciate how both sources start being distinguished 3 mm apart and are perfectly disentangled at 4 mm separation (Fig. 12). These results are compatible with the FWHM spatial resolution obtained for a single point source.

Fig. 12. Reconstructed images of two point sources of 1 mm diameter at different separations (2 mm, 3 mm, 4 mm and 5 mm) with displaced detectors.

We have evaluated the center-to-center measured distance of the radial profile with respect to the nominal separation between the sources. At 5 mm separation, we have obtained $5.02 \text{ mm} \pm 0.03 \text{ mm}$ center-to-center distance (Fig. 13), whereas at 4 mm separation we have measured a distance of $4.18 \text{ mm} \pm 0.06 \text{ mm}$, which is compatible with the position of the sources.

Fig. 13. An example of the radial profile obtained from two 1.0 mm diameter ^{22}Na point sources acquired simultaneously at 5 mm separation.

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

We have evaluated the performance of a simple PET demonstrator under coincidence operation using two monolithic blocks with ASIC readout. Our results indicate that the spatial resolution of individual detectors is sufficient for our application and that our dedicated front-end ASIC is suitable for coincidence trigger PET data taking. The detector

blocks behave according to specifications, with energy resolutions of 13.2 % FWHM at 511 keV and ASIC self-triggering adequate for PET coincidence operation, as required. Our laboratory setup shows a timing resolution under coincidence operation of 27 ns FWHM, expected to improve down to a few ns after replacement of our current ASIC based on leading-edge discriminator logic by an updated version which includes a CFD. We have achieved reconstructed spatial resolutions as good as 2.1 mm FWHM for ^{22}Na point sources by using SSRB and FBP. Moreover, we have presented the imaging capabilities of the monolithic detector block design and its resolving power by reconstructing images of two point sources acquired simultaneously. The results obtained validate the principle of operation of our BrainPET scanner presently under development. This scanner will be a PET insert compatible with MRI which will be installed in a collaborating hospital.

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